

A Novel Technic for Detecting the Degradation in Photovoltaic Modul

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Abstract

This study presents a novel and cost-effective technique for detecting degradation in photovoltaic (PV) modules using ultraviolet (UV) light-emitting diodes (LEDs). PV modules are widely used for sustainable energy generation; however, environmental factors such as ultraviolet radiation, temperature fluctuations, humidity, and water penetration significantly reduce their efficiency and operational lifetime. In this research, a custom-designed fault detection system was developed, consisting of UV LEDs (390–410 nm), an OPT101 photodiode sensor, an Arduino-based control unit, and a MATLAB-based user interface. The system was experimentally tested under Standard Test Conditions (STC: 1000 W m⁻², 25 °C) on 40 W polycrystalline silicon modules. The proposed method focuses on detecting surface color changes, microcracks, and snail trail formations, which are common indicators of PV module deterioration. Experimental results demonstrate that the UV-based detection approach is more effective, lightweight, and economical compared to traditional fault detection techniques such as infrared thermography and electroluminescence imaging. The system successfully identifies degradation by measuring reflected light intensity and visually mapping affected areas. This approach enables efficient maintenance strategies for PV systems, improving energy yield and reducing long-term operational costs. As future work, the developed detection system can be integrated with autonomous robots for large-scale PV plant monitoring, enabling continuous and non-invasive performance diagnostics.

Keywords: UV led, degradation, solar pv, snail trail

1. Introduction

In the age of industry, private homes, transportation, personal computers, and the Fourth Industrial Revolution, energy demand is rapidly increasing. Experts predict that solar PV capacity will continue to grow rapidly, reaching approximately 10 TW by 2030 and 30 to 70 TW by 2050 (Haegel et al., 2019). PV modules, recognized for their sustainability and environmental benefits, are extensively utilized in industrial, commercial, and residential sectors (Adıgüzel et al., 2019; Mahto et al., 2020). In response to the growing popularity of photovoltaic-based energy, several research have been undertaken in the literature to enhance the performance and decrease the cost of photovoltaic modules (Zulkefli et al., 2017; Yamaguchi et al., 2018; Akyazı et al., 2019). Although numerous PV performance studies have been conducted globally, PV modules remain susceptible to several environmental factors (such as partial shadowing, elevated temperatures, irradiance fluctuations, collected dust, and ultraviolet radiation) that diminish their effectiveness (Chaichan et al., 2018; Patel et al., 2019). The total power output diminishes by around 0.5% to 0.05% for each 1 °C rise in temperature. The effectiveness of the photovoltaic panel diminishes in accordance with the extent of shaded region (Irwanto et al., 2014). Moreover, dust, defined as solid particles with sizes less than 500 µm, is a crucial factor affecting the efficiency of photovoltaic systems. It arises from several natural sources in the atmosphere, and these particles may comprise animal and human cells, sand, organic materials, clay, ash, and other substances (Mani and Pillai, 2010; Adinoyi and Said, 2013). Photovoltaic modules are constructed by interconnecting an array of solar cells both in series and in parallel. The efficiency and cost of photovoltaic cells fluctuate based on the materials employed. Certain experimental photovoltaic cells exhibit an efficiency approaching 40% (Ehrler et al., 2020). In the field, the typical energy conversion efficiency of used PV modules ranges from 20% to 30% (Werner, 2022). Widely used materials in PV panels include

monocrystalline and polycrystalline silicon, which are traditional crystalline silicon-based technologies. Additionally, emerging thin-film technologies utilize materials such as cadmium telluride (CdTe) and copper indium gallium selenide (CIGS). Furthermore, perovskite solar cells are gaining attention as alternative materials. The performance of these panels is also enhanced by transparent conductive materials, encapsulation polymers, and antireflective coatings, which contribute to their efficiency and durability (Dallaev et al., 2023). Additionally, organic photovoltaic modules utilizing gallium arsenide are commercially accessible. High-efficiency energy harvesting may be achieved from a GaAs-based organic module by using the infrared transparency window inside the 650 nm to 950 nm wavelength range (Moon et al., 2017). The operational lifespan of PV modules can be extended from 30 to 40 years through an enhanced lamination process in their production (Paç and Gok, 2024). Nevertheless, PV modules encounter many external stressors that might impact their functional qualities and result in diminished solar cell efficiency (Chaichan et al., 2018; Omazic et al., 2019). Photovoltaic module manufacturers indicate that at 1000 W m⁻², a temperature of 25 °C, and an air mass of 1.5, a PV module achieves optimal performance. These characteristics are employed by several researchers as a standard test condition (STC) in their investigations. Recent literature indicates a growing number of investigations on the deterioration of PV modules (Al Mahdi et al., 2023; Rahman et al., 2023; Alam et al., 2024). Ethylene Vinyl Acetate (EVA) is the predominant encapsulating material for back sheets in photovoltaic modules (Peike et al., 2011). While increased temperature and UV irradiation progressively diminish stabilizer concentration, the use of UV stabilizers and antioxidants may enhance its operational longevity (Meyer and Van Dyk, 2004). External variables, including UV irradiation, temperature fluctuations, and humidity, contribute to the depreciation and aging of photovoltaic modules. Figure 1 illustrates the chemical structure of EVA.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of EVA

The chemical structure of EVA may have twenty or more ethylene blocks. Additionally, it may be synthesized using various vinyl acetate blocks. The deterioration processes, including color changes, may be attributed to UV light and water infiltration in the combined module at temperatures over 50 °C (Oreski and Wallner, 2009). Furthermore, chemical processes may be initiated mostly by ultraviolet (UV) light. Consequently, prevalent EVA concerns in photovoltaic modules may be emphasized as follows (Oliveira et al., 2018):

- Yellowing.
- Delamination.
- Bubbles.
- Defects in the anti-reflective coating.
- Burnt cells.
- Bypass diode failure
- Moisture-induced degradations.

In a laboratory investigation, four PV back sheet layers of comparable size were subjected to varying durations of exposure to short wavelengths ranging from 365 nm to 295 nm. Test findings indicate observable bodily changes, including yellowing and aging (Liu et al., 2014). The deterioration diminishes light access to the photovoltaic cell, resulting in a significant reduction in the module's output power (Ndiaye et al., 2013). Moreover, ultraviolet radiation alters the molecular structure of organic photovoltaic modules, resulting in a reduction in photocurrent at

elevated photon energies (Patel et al., 2019). The deterioration of PV modules is not solely influenced by external causes, as a 12% degradation was noted in PV modules even under storage conditions over a span of 30 years (Liu et al., 2019). Energy efficiency is crucial, and it is equally vital to monitor and identify degradations in photovoltaic modules. These assessments can be performed using visual examination, digital imaging with ultraviolet light illumination, current-voltage curve analysis, infrared thermography, and electroluminescence imaging (Kaplani, 2016). The snail trails represent a form of micro-cracking within the cells of the modules. Figure 2 illustrates a photovoltaic module exhibiting snail track damage. Not all micro-cracks will be recognized as snail tracks. However, if a photovoltaic module cell exhibits a snail trail on its surface, it contains microcracks (Liu et al., 2019). Micro-cracks resulting from little fissures in cells are generally not discernible to the naked eye. While color alterations may appear linear within the cell, the fractures remain imperceptible to the naked eye. If a photovoltaic module exhibits various colored lines, electroluminescence testing (ELCD; Electroluminescence Crack Detection Test) can be conducted to identify micro-crack failures. Electroluminescence is an optical and electrical phenomena in which a substance emits light when an electric current passes through it or a strong electric field is placed

across it. It operates based on the principles of optics (Haque et al., 2019). The emission is diminished in locations with microcracks, resulting in darker regions in electroluminescence (EL) (Bakir, 2023). The maximum power output from snail trails might diminish by up to 37%. Additionally, annual

electricity output may decrease by as much as 32% (Dolara et al., 2014). Consequently, the presence of snail tracks on photovoltaic modules may be regarded as a significant flaw in the modules.

Figure 2. Visible picture of snail trail

In addition, the uncontrolled chemical reaction which is triggered by UV radiation and water penetration causes browning or

yellowing of the plastic materials on the panel which is shown in Figure. 3.

Figure 3. Browning and yellowing fault

This research examines the detection of color changes and the phenomena of snail trails in solar photovoltaic modules using ultraviolet light-emitting diodes (390-410 nm). The front glass of the photovoltaic module utilized for ultraviolet filtration is cerium glass and tempered glass. A user interface application is built using MATLAB software to identify the color-changing phenomena and snail trails of solar modules. The application successfully executed duties on the solar photovoltaic modules.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Material

This system exhibits an experimental investigation utilizing a specified wavelength to detect the resultant reflection. To find PV modules with surface cracks (caused by snail trails) and color variations, a rectangular detector box has been made. It is seen in Figure 4. The electrical specifications of photovoltaic modules from datasheets are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The PV module parameters

Electrical Data	SL040-12P
Cell type	Polycrystalline
Maximum power (Pmax)	40W
Maximum power voltage (Vmp)	18V
Maximum power current (Imp)	2.22A
Open circuit voltage (Voc)	21.6 V
Short circuit current (Isc)	2.44A
Number of cells	36

The system mainly consists of

- six UV LEDs,
- an Arduino electronics platform is used as controller,
- an OPT101 photodiode,
- a battery recharged,
- a display,
- a buzzer,
- a rectangular prism shape box, and
- an on-off switch

Figure 4. The fault detection system

Figure 5, 6 delineates the overall design of the device and illustrates the spectral range of the photodiode. The primary control function has been implemented using Arduino. OPT101 and UV LEDs serve as supplementary components for the system, holding equal significance to the controller. Furthermore, the display and buzzer have been utilized as alert mechanisms inside the system. OPT101 is a type of detector commonly utilized for the

assessment of physical materials (Lee and Pourrezaei, 2016). The light-sensitive region is 2.286 x 2.286 mm (Wasif, 2015). The reflected light from the surface of the PV modules is transferred to them. The used UV LED spectrum falls inside this area. The selection of 390-410nm UV LEDs is due to their proximity to the electroluminescence (EL) spectrum and their cost-effectiveness.

Figure 6. The fault detection system

There are seven wavelength ranges which are assigned to different colors. When we move from red to violet, energies of spectrum are increased the wavelength of spectrum decreases.

Different types of wavelength ranges are given below:

- Violet: 400-420 nm
- Indigo: 420 - 440 nm
- Blue: 440 - 490 nm
- Green: 490 - 570 nm
- Yellow: 570 - 585 nm
- Orange: 585 - 620 nm
- Red: 620 - 780 nm

Figure 6. Visible spectrum

Additionally, ultraviolet (UV) light is categorized into three types based on wavelength: UV-A (longwave UV; 315-400 nm), UV-B (mediumwave UV; 280-315 nm), and UV-C (shortwave UV; 200-280 nm). The most harsh wavelength, due to induced

polymer problems, is UV-B. This study selects a 1W power UV-A LED for its cost-effectiveness, availability, and application. Furthermore, its spectral energy exceeds that of the visible spectrum. Thus, it is desired to notice the micro-crack regions and areas of

color variation under a high and secure spectrum. Another rationale for selecting this LED is its diminished efficacy when exposed through a glass/EVA filter (Gagliardi et al.,

2017). The selected UV LED is seen in Figure 7. The working voltage is 3V, the direct current is 350mA, and the wavelength ranges from 390 to 410 nm.

Figure 7. Edixeon S series 1W Power UV led.

OPT 101 optical sensors are utilized for assessing physical materials. The data acquired from test materials is employed to determine the optical reflection, absorption, or transmission properties of the materials at

certain wavelengths. Figure 8 depicts the apparatus utilized for evaluating the optical reflective properties of a test material. The datasheet includes configuration details for the OPT101.

Figure 8. Fixture for measurement of optical reflective properties of a test material

Moreover, the OPT101 datasheet indicates that the materials exhibiting various hues inside the fixture provide insights on the optical reflective characteristics of such materials. Its technical specification is given in Table 2. Figure 9 demonstrates that the color with the longest wavelength, red, has the most

contrast. Contrarily, the green findings exhibit the lowest contrast. This approach effectively detects color reflections on materials of varying hues, and our experimental setup is applicable for identifying deterioration in photovoltaic modules.

Figure 9. Sorted test materials for OPT101

In our test study, a shield was used to mount OPT 101 sensors on an Arduino. An electronic card has UV LEDs mounted on it in the shape of a ring. Both have been positioned at a 45-

degree angle on either side of the box (Figure 10). Because it allows light from LEDs to be reflected off the surfaces of PV modules, they are positioned at a 45-degree angle.

Table 2. The technical specifications of OPT101

Specification	Value
Supply Voltage Range	2.7V - 36V
Quiescent Current	~120 μ A
Photodiode Active Area	2.29 mm x 2.29 mm
Operating Temperature Range	0 $^{\circ}$ C - 70 $^{\circ}$ C

This specific design delivers around 92% light to the photodiode. Consequently, micro-cracks attributed to snail trails and corresponding color alterations were attempted to be extracted from PV module surfaces. In

comparison to EL testing, PV modules exhibiting micro-cracks are anticipated to have a deeper hue during UV LED inspection as well.

Figure 10. Response vs Incident Angle

Figure 11 presents the specific responsivity curve of the OPT101. While it permits a high sensitivity range from 230nm to 1100nm, the testing setup utilized a range between 390nm

and 410nm. Furthermore, because it has an internal voltage amplifier, no external voltage amplifier is necessary.

Figure 11. Spectral responsivity of OPT101

2.2. Methods

Numerous works in the literature are focused on developing a programming interface for detecting deterioration in photovoltaic modules (Dhimish, 2018; Akyazi et al., 2019). Consequently, deterioration detection may be executed automatically with the assistance of the program. To this end, we created software that is integral to the system delivering information on the state of the PV

module. The software interface has two components. One is being created in MATLAB/GUI, while the other is being built on the Arduino platform. The system is engineered to interpret the computer's serial port via Arduino analog data. The MATLAB/GUI and the controller interact via the serial port. Figure 12 illustrates the MATLAB/GUI interface alongside the computational flowchart of the Arduino program.

Figure 12. User interface and algorithmic flow chart used for detecting degradation of PV modules

Figure 13 illustrates the flowchart for identifying the deterioration of photovoltaic modules. The operational principle is fundamentally straightforward. The photodiode's output voltage varies with the light intensity. The nominal operating value is established prior to initiating deterioration

detection. Subsequently, the deterioration detection box is positioned to go directly along the PV module. If the acquired data significantly deviates from the nominal value, it can be concluded that a distortion exists inside that region.

Figure 13. Algorithmic flow chart

3. Results

The primary aim of this study is to identify the deterioration of photovoltaic modules. The results from the user interface software indicate that light reflected from the color-changing cell region may be readily detected by the photodiode components. Figure 14 illustrates two distinct surfaces within the

photovoltaic modules. Fig. 16(A) exhibits a uniform appearance of the PV module, whereas Fig. 16(B) displays a non-uniform color appearance. The homogeneous and nonhomogeneous photovoltaic modules have been analyzed using this approach, and the findings are presented in Figures 15, 16, 20, and 21. Figure 22 presents a reference value for comparison with the observational data.

Figure 14. PV modules having two different surfaces

Figure 15. PV modules output voltages and time graphs

Figure 16. PV modules surfaces temperature and time graphs

Figures 15 and 16 illustrate an inverse relationship between the rise in surface temperature of the modules and the output voltage. This phenomenon is most evident

during 14:00 and 16:00 hours. The surface temperature has been measured using the Optris Pi160 thermal camera. Its technical specifications of the Optris Pi160 is given in Table3.

Table 3. The technical specifications of the Optris Pi160.

Specification	Value
Optical Resolution	160 × 120 pixels
Detector Type	FPA
Spectral Range	8 – 14 μm
Frame Rate	120 Hz
Field of View	23° × 17° (f = 10 mm)

Figure 17 illustrates the block diagram of the testing platform. Thermal imaging is a non-contact technique for monitoring module

temperature and identifying faults. This approach may not consistently identify microfractures on the panel.

Figure 17. Block diagram of test platform.

The distance between the infrared camera and the photovoltaic panel is two meters. The panel is positioned around 90 degrees relative to the camera. Figure 18(A) pertains to the

homogeneous module, while Figure 18(B) pertains to the nonhomogeneous module. The distinction between the two modules cannot be determined by thermal imaging.

Figure 18. Thermal images of PV modules

This study shows that use UV LED to detect deterioration in solar modules is the simplest and most conclusive method. Figure 19 illustrates the ultraviolet picture of the photovoltaic module. The nonhomogeneous

look is well shown in the image. The illustration in Fig. 20 was produced by relocating the deterioration detection box from the upper to the lower section of the numbered surface.

Figure 19. UV reflection image

Figure 20. Observation data from nonhomogeneous module surface

The mean value is derived from traversing the uniform surface of the PV module. Figure 21 illustrates the graphical outcomes of a

standard (homogeneous) photovoltaic module. It serves as a reference value for the detecting system.

Figure 21. Reference value from homogeneous PV module

4. Conclusion

We present a microcontroller-based degradation detecting system on PV modules which is both cost and lightweight effective. As an alternative to image processing with thermal imager which is one of the classical fault detection methods, UV detection is deployed in the present study. The user interface is created with MATLAB software. The surface of the photovoltaic panel is scanned and plotted on the screen and in the UV spectrum range (390nm-400nm), color changes and snail trails are detected. By using this method, significant visual changes on the surface of PV modules can be detected in a cost-efficient way, since surface cracks and color changes are quite significant problems

for the PV plants due to the reduction of power efficiency. As a future work, the system developed can also be placed on an autonomous robot for performing PV plant control.

Declaration of Author Contributions

This study was created from the author's Ph.D. thesis. A.E.C. wrote the paper. A.E.C performed the experiments., A.E.C. and M.R.T. analyzed the data., A.E.C. and M.R.T. contributed materials tools., M.R.T. critically reviewed the manuscript.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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